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EFFECTS OF BLINDNESS AWARENESS PROGRAMME ON ATTITUDE OF SIGHTED STUDENTS TOWARDS STUDENTS WITH VISUAL IMPAIRMENT IN UNIVERSITY OF JOS, PLATEAU STATE

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Abstract: The thrust of this study was to investigate the effects of blindness awareness programme on attitude of students towards students with visual impairment in the University of Jos, Plateau State. The objective of the study was to find out if blindness awareness programme could change the attitude of the sighted students towards students with visual impairment in University of Jos, Plateau State. Two research questions and two hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The Non-equivalent groups quasi experimental research design was adopted. The population for the study was 100 students in the inclusive setting of University of Jos Plateau State. Sixty (60) sighted students were sampled out of 100 students. Simple random sampling techniques was used. One instrument was used for the study titled: Attitude toward the blind students (ATBS). The data collected were analyze using the chi-square statistic at 0.5 level of significance. The results showed that there was positive attitudinal change of sighted students towards students with visual impairment in university of Jos, Plateau State. The study shows that to a great extent ATBS has changed the attitude of sighted students towards students with visual impairment in university of Jos, Plateau State. It is therefore recommended blindness awareness programme (BAP) be used to change the attitude of sighted students towards students with visual impairment.

Keywords: Blindness, Awareness Programme, Attitude, Sighted Students and Students with Visual Impairment.

Background to the Study

Persons with special needs have been subjected to different forms of maltreatment from time immemorial and there is documented evidence of this social injustice. According to Kisanji (2020), history is replete with instances of persons with special needs worldwide who were ridiculed, killed, and abandoned to die or condemned to permanent exclusion in asylums. The Greeks abandoned persons with special needs to drown in rivers. In Europe, Nero Commodious is said to have shot bows and arrows on persons with physical disabilities and that the church in the 15th century sanctioned the extermination of people with special needs. Coleridge (2002) traces through history the killing of people with special needs beginning with the Spartans who killed persons with special needs as a matter of law; the endorsement by Martin Luther to kill babies with special needs because they were incarnations of the devil. The English Eugenicists who eliminated persons with special needs under the Darwinian evolution theory of survival of the fittest and the Nazi euthanasia programme under Hitler. Who exterminated persons with special needs on the pretense that they could not make contribution to the society are instances of society's attitude towards persons with special needs.

In Nigeria, it was nothing different as persons with special needs were thrown into the evil forest to die, and even some were killed as they were seen as evil children (Ki Sanji, 2020). Attitude is a triolelement concept embodying beliefs, emotions and behavior which characterize human beings in intra-personal and in social interaction. Attitudes are formed as a result of information/ misinformation about certain attitude objects. People form likes and dislike not necessarily as a result of their contact with the attitude object but as a result of information they get regarding the object from other people such as parents, peers or other older adults who themselves may not have had contacts or enough information about the object. The information they have about the object may have been passed to them by their own parents or other significant adults of their environment.

Some attitudes may also be formed due to knowledge and contact with the people whom the attitude is directed towards. In all, attitudes could be learnt and as a result could also be unlearned. The information we glean from the media such as the television, films, radio, journals, magazines and newspapers go a long way in dictating and directing our attitude toward certain people or persons, objects and phenomena. Likes and dislikes are formed as early as the childhood stages during which children imitate the significant adults in their environment. Children begin to prefer certain persons to the others learn differences in physique and attach themselves to models. Most of their actions are dictated not just by knowledge but by some kind of indoctrination or uniformed reactions to the attitude object.

Hence psychologists believe that one's beliefs, affect and behaviour dispositions can be altered using techniques found in theory and research since attitudes are learned and are predicable (Ozaji, 1991). Attitudes toward persons with special needs can be changed either incongruently (i.e. from positive to negative or negative to positive) or congruently (i.e. increasing the negativity/positivity of an existing attitude) (Ozaji & Mugu, 1999). Attitude change means the acquisition, reversal or intensification of an attitude (Johnson & Matros 1975; Ozaji, 1991).

Attitude change means the acquisition, reversal or intensification of an attitude (Ozaji & Mugu, 1999). Formation of an attitude is also integral to change in attitudes, as individuals acquire new experiences and information, attitudes undergo continual change which have necessitated theories and techniques used in planned attitude change towards persons with special needs which the researcher tries to explore through the use of role play and bibliotherapy. Thus, attitudes and beliefs are present in everyone. These can be formed from a number of sources and can impact how people

interact with each other. Having meaningful interactions with students with visual impairment lead to people developing positive attitudes as well. Attitude issues in the life of people with visual impairment are of great importance. Both those who are with visual impairment and those who support people with disability face attitude problem. For example, the researcher's friend on a visit could not accept drinking water in the house because it was an environment of a school for blind children. The friend is a teacher by profession. Supposing he is to teach the child with blindness geometry, definitely he would not cope.

Sardegna and Paul (2021) found out that cultural expectations of "normality" have put pressure on impairment. National Institute for Visual Handicapped (NIVH) (2012) found that a lot of literature review showed that the maladjustment of persons with visual impairment is not due to actual visual impairment but due to the attitudes of the sighted toward the blind and due to the emotional stress placed on them by the sighted in social situations. Any students with visual impairment who went to school may never be whole-heartedly accepted at any level that he indicated interest in because of the attitude of people. Students with visual impairment often met with resentment by the school authority or the department. As Nemeth (2016) confirmed, that such people are often of the view that person with blindness cannot cope in school.

Ozaji (1991) opined that attitude is a tri-element concept. This simply means attitudes are made up of three inter – related parts (Ozaji, 1996). They are our beliefs, our feelings and our behaviours or actions towards a person, or object. Webster dictionary defines attitude as a measured disposition, feeling, and position with regard to a person or thing. It is a learned predisposition to behave in a consistent evaluative manner towards a person, an object or a group of objects. This evaluation can be favourable or unfavorable, positive or negative directed to certain people, issues or institutions (NIVH, 2019). From the history of the education of children with blindness in Nigeria, people have come across the educational provision of the "blind" without mathematics. Therefore, any thought of teaching mathematics to the "blind" in Nigeria will be met with negative attitude. This is because attitude can be a relative enduring organisation of beliefs around an object or situation predisposing one to respond in some preferential manners (Ozaji, 1991).

Attitudes are social but not static. They are formed in social groups and are about other people and can affect our relationships with others. Some societies are more accommodating to persons with blindness than others. This depends on their thinking and feeling based on their beliefs. Attitude may involve a prejudice in which we perceive an issue or person without giving unbiased consideration to all the evidence. This prejudice leads to an unrealistic judgment based on inadequate grounds (NIVH, 2019). Just because some students have never seen a student with blindness in school that means students with blindness cannot be in school. The attitude of sighted students towards their counterparts with visual impairment are expressed in the way the sighted treat, relegate, neglect, label, stigmatize, devalue, discriminate and deprive them of their rights. For instance, instead of addressing them by their names, the sighted will nickname them "blind students". In fact, at some point the sighted students called students with visual impairment "blind male and female students" (Gender).

The concept of impairment in this study is about children who have damaged organ of vision such that it affects their learning there by resulting in adaptation of teaching methods, materials and learning process. Abang (2005) stated that impairment can prevent an individual from functioning in a particular or given situation. This view supports the view that educationally impairment is seen towards issues of restrictions in functioning educationally, socially, and in doing certain activities in life.

Carroll (2020) defined blindness as the measurement that the visual acuity does not exceed 20/200 (6/60) or less in the better eye with the best possible correction or field of vision that is restricted to an angle extending an arc of 20 degrees or less. This is a legal definition. Legal definition is used in rehabilitation. It is referred to as definition for eligibility for services. This definition is needed for allocating resources for states in America who provide rehabilitation services to persons with visual impairment. Unfortunately, such approach is not available in Nigeria. Legal definition is not well comprehended in our special residential schools in Nigeria. No school is provided equipment or materials based on the degree of impairment of its children based on visual acuity measurement.

Mwapishak (2025) holds that Blindness Awareness Programme (BAP) is a programme designed to educate and enlightened student about the change of attitude of sighted students towards students with visual impairment. It can help improve knowledge, attitudes and acceptance of people with visual impairment. There have been a wide variety of formats of blindness awareness programme including providing information about visual impairment through videos, drama, theatre and puppet shows, discussions, stories, simulations, structured interactions and classroom activities among others. The outcomes of such blindness awareness programme are mixed. For example, some researchers have found a positive change in attitudes toward students with visual impairment following a blindness awareness programme, while others have reported that there was no change. Despite the growing literature on the inclusion of students with visual impairment in mainstream classrooms and the subsequent increase in blindness awareness programme, the common elements of the effective components have not been synthesized and remain largely unknown.

Indeed, little attention has been paid to effective strategies to promote positive attitudes towards their peers with visual impairment. It is critical that blindness awareness programme is effective so that they can provide typically developing students with opportunities to learn and develop positive attitudes about differences in a respectful context. Helping students nurture such attitudes at school can contribute to the creation of a positive social climate among students and youth. Addressing attitudes towards students with visual impairment is very important because at this age their attitudes are still evolving and early programme may be especially beneficial. The study seeks to find out if blindness awareness programme can change the attitude of sighted students towards students with visual impairment in University of Jos.

Statement of the Problems

Students with visual impairment are mostly not understood on their proper perspective. This situation leads to stereotypes, myths, negative attitude toward them. At the root of this contest is ignorance. The statement of this problem is that the sighted students exhibit negative attitudes towards their peers with visual impairment. There is also a circle of low expectation on the ability of the students with visual impairment. Helen Keller opined that blindness is not what worries her most but the attitudes the public displays towards visual impairment. Again, sight brings face hand information and also 75% of learning takes place through the sight but where the sight is not there it poses a big impediment.

the role of the family, peers, and caregivers in child development differ for instance in the extent to which peers and family autonomy is respected, in the degree of family instruction or parental coaching, and in the attention paid to parent–infant interaction can make a difference in the lives of others.

Following this statement, it means that the students with visual impairment have a series of problems considering the attitudes of the sighted students, where it is negative, it grossly affects the students with visual impairment and it is more dangerous where attitude and feelings of the sighted

students is also negative. The problem of this study, therefore, is to find out the effects of blindness awareness programme on the attitude of sighted students towards students with visual impairment in the University of Jos, Plateau State

Objectives of the Study

The purpose of this study is to find out effects of blindness awareness programme on attitude of sighted students towards students with visual impairment in the University of Jos, Plateau State. Specifically, the study is based on the following objectives:

1. To determine the pretest and posttest attitude mean scores of students in experimental and control groups.
2. To find out the pretest and posttest attitude mean scores of male and female students on experimental.

Research Questions

The following research questions are formulated to guide the study:

1. What is the pretest and posttest attitude direction mean scores of students in experimental and control group?
2. What is the pretest and posttest attitude direction mean scores of male and female students in experimental?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference between attitude direction mean scores of sighted students in experimental and control groups.
2. There is no significant difference between attitude direction mean scores of male and female students in experimental group after intervention using BAP.

Methodology

Research Design

The study is experimental research. It adopted the non-equivalent quasi experimental research design.

Population of the Study

The population of the study was made up of 100 sighted students in the inclusive setting of University of Jos Plateau State.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The researcher samples a total of sixty (60) sighted students out of 100 students respectively for this study. Random sampling techniques was used to selects a subset of sixty (60) one hundred (100) level from students.

Instrumentation

The researcher developed two instruments and were used for this study. The instruments are: Blindness Awareness Programme (BAP) and Attitude toward the blind students (ATBS).

Validity of the Instruments

The validity of the instruments was generated to be 0.816 for (BAP) and 0.888 for ATBS.

Reliability of the Instruments

The reliability of the instruments obtained using Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient index was 0.829 for both (BAP) and 0.888 for ATBS.

Procedure for Data Collection / Treatment

The treatment programme on Blindness Awareness Programme (BAP) and Attitude Towards Blind Students (ATBS) was done by the researcher at both pretest and posttest respectively. The experimental group were exposed to Blindness Awareness Programme while conventional method of teaching was used to those in the control group.

Data Analysis

The data collected for this study were subjected to chi-square statistics which is a powerful tool for investigating relationships between categorical variables.

Results

Research Question One

What is the pretest and posttest attitude direction mean scores of students in experimental and control group?

Table 1: Pretest and Post-Test Attitude Direction Mean Scores of Students in Experimental and Control Groups

S/N	Statements	N	EXPERIMENTAL				CONTROL			
			pre-test mean	SD	Post-Test mean	SD	Pretest mean	SD	Post-test mean	SD
1	I share the feeling that educated students with visual impairment should be given opportunity to work.	30	1.62	0.49	2.77	0.98	1.63	0.50	1.93	1.00
2	I feel happy whenever I help students with visual impairment.	30	1.62	0.49	2.62	1.01	1.67	0.50	1.80	1.01
3	I like the idea to hide students with visual impairment in the house.	30	1.80	0.40	1.95	0.59	1.87	0.40	1.03	0.60
4	I shall be happy to see students with visual impairment in the club.	30	1.55	0.50	2.20	1.04	1.60	0.51	2.00	1.06

5	I naturally dislike students with visual impairment.	30	1.43	0.50	1.70	0.87	1.50	0.51	1.80	0.89
6	I feel comfortable to live in the same house with students with visual impairment.	30	1.25	0.44	3.02	1.23	1.27	0.43	2.17	1.24
7	If my son/daughter wishes to marry a student with visual impairment, I may wish to stop that marriage.	30	1.62	0.49	1.98	0.87	1.67	0.50	2.10	0.91
8	I share the feeling that students with visual impairment should be educated.	30	1.62	0.49	2.77	0.98	1.63	0.50	1.93	1.00

Note: Mean scores below 2.5 is disagree and above 2.5 is agreed

Table 1 from the data analyzed before intervention in both experimental and control groups respondents responses showed that items 1,2,7, and 8 had mean scores of 1.62 ± 0.49 , while item 3 had mean scores of 1.80 ± 0.40 ; item 4 had mean scores of 1.55 ± 0.50 , item 5 had a mean score of 1.43 ± 0.50 and item 6 had a mean score of 1.25 ± 0.44 all which implies that majority of the students disagreed which mean they show negative attitude towards students with visual impairment in both experimental and control groups.

After intervention, respondents in the experimental group had a change of attitude on item 6 had the highest mean score value of 3.02 ± 1.23 that they feel comfortable to live in the same house with students with visual impairment to a high extent. Item 1 and 8 had post-test mean scores of 2.77 ± 0.98 which indicates that “they share the feeling that educated students with visual impairment should be given opportunity to work” and “they share the feeling that students with visual impairment should be educated” to a moderate extent. The least post-test mean scores was 1.70 ± 0.87 on that “they naturally dislike students with visual impairment” which means that they disagreed with the statement. While students in the control group had below mean scores 2.5.

Research Question Two

What is the pretest and post-test attitude mean scores of male and female students in experimental?

Table 2: Pretest and Post-test Attitude Mean Scores of Male and Female Students in Experimental

Gender	N	Pretest Mean	SD	Posttest Mean	SD	Mean Gain	Posttest Mean Difference
Male	10	1.62	0.49	3.02	1.23	1.40	0.15
Female	15	1.80	0.40	3.17	1.24	1.37	

Table 2 shows the Pretest and Post-test Attitude Mean Scores of Male and Female Students in Experimental. The Male had an attitude pretest mean scores of 1.62 ± 0.49 and attitude post mean scores of 3.02 ± 1.23 with mean gain of 1.40, while female had an attitude pretest mean scores of 1.80 ± 0.40 and attitude post-test mean scores of 3.17 ± 1.24 with a mean gain score of 1.37. This implies that male students had a little higher post-test mean scores difference of 0.15 than female

Hypothesis One

There is no significant difference between attitude mean scores of sighted students in experimental and control groups.

Table 3: t-test Analysis on Attitude Post-test Mean Scores of Sighted Students in Experimental and Control Group

Groups	N	X	SD	Df	t-value	P-value
Experimental	30	2.38	0.48	58	3.955	0.001
Control	30	1.51	0.39			

Table 3 showed the t-test Analysis on Attitude Post-test Mean Scores of Sighted Students in Experimental and Control Group. Experimental group had a post-test mean scores of 2.38 and standard deviation 0.48 and control group had a posttest mean scores of 1.51 and standard deviation of 0.39. This implies there is a significant difference between attitude mean scores of sighted students in experimental and control groups in favour of experimental group.

Hypothesis Two

There is no significant difference between attitude mean scores of male and female students in experimental group.

Table 4: t-test Analysis on Attitude Post-test Mean Scores of Male and Female Students in Experimental Group.

Groups	N	X	SD	Df	t-value	P-value
Male	15	3.45	0.44	28	.300	.774
Female	15	3.33	0.55			

Table 4 showed the t-test Analysis on Attitude Post-test Mean Scores of Male and Female Students in Experimental Group. Male had a post-test mean scores of 3.45 and standard deviation 0.44 and females had a posttest mean scores of 3.33 and standard deviation of 0.55 with a t-value of 0.30 and a p-value 0.774. This implies there is no significant difference between attitudes mean scores of male and female students in experimental group.

Discussion

In this study, the two (2) research questions and two (2) hypotheses were aimed at investigating the effects of Blindness Awareness Programme (BAP) on the attitude of sighted students towards students with visual impairment in University of Jos, Plateau State. The findings of Research Question One in Table 1 from the data analyzed before intervention in both experimental and control groups respondents responses showed that items 1,2,7, and 8 had mean scores of 1.62 ± 0.49 , while item 3 had mean scores of 1.80 ± 0.40 ; item 4 had mean scores of 1.55 ± 0.50 , item 5 had a mean score of 1.43 ± 0.50 and item 6 had a mean score of 1.25 ± 0.44 all which implies that majority of the students disagreed which mean they show negative attitude towards students with visual impairment in both experimental and control groups.

After intervention, respondents in the experimental group had a change of attitude on item 6 had the highest mean score value of 3.02 ± 1.23 that they feel comfortable to live in the same house with students with visual impairment to a high extent. Item 1 and 8 had post-test mean scores of 2.77 ± 0.98 which indicates that “they share the feeling that educated students with visual impairment should be given opportunity to work” and “they share the feeling that students with visual impairment should be educated” to a moderate extent. The least post-test mean scores was 1.70 ± 0.87 on that “they naturally dislike students with visual impairment” which means that they disagreed with the statement. While students in the control group had below mean scores 2.5.

Similarly, research suggested that adolescent girls tend to have more positive attitudes change towards students with visually impairment than the adolescent boys (Bossert, Colping, Piji and Petry, 2011). On the contrary, other research indicated that undergraduate males have more negative implicit attitudes towards the students with visual impairment than sighted men students, adding that gender may be one factor for predicting attitudes.

The findings of Research Question Two in Table 2, showed the Pretest and Post-test Attitude Mean Scores of Male and Female Students in Experimental. The Male had an attitude pretest mean scores of 1.62 ± 0.49 and attitude post mean scores of 3.02 ± 1.23 with mean gain of 1.40, while female had a attitude pretest mean scores of 1.80 ± 0.40 and attitude post-test mean scores of 3.17 ± 1.24 with a mean gain score of 1.37. This implies that male students had a little higher post-test mean scores difference of 0.15 than female.

The findings of Hypothesis One in Table 3, showed the t-test Analysis on Attitude Post-test Mean Scores of Sighted Students in Experimental and Control Group. Experimental group had a post-test mean scores of 2.38 and standard deviation 0.48 and control group had a posttest mean scores of 1.51 and standard deviation of 0.39 with a t-value of 3.955 with a p-value 0.001. This implies there is a significant difference between attitude mean scores of sighted students in experimental and control groups in favour of experimental group.

The findings of Hypothesis Two in Table 4, showed the t-test Analysis on Attitude Post-test Mean Scores of Male and Female Students in Experimental Group. Male had a post-test mean scores of 3.45 and standard deviation 0.44 and females had a posttest mean scores of 3.33 and standard deviation of 0.55 with a t-value of 0.30 with a p-value 0.774. This implies there is no significant difference between attitudes mean scores of male and female students in experimental group.

The second hypothesis revealed that there is no significant difference between the sighted students' attitudes towards students with visual impairment based on onset. Supporting this, Jurmang (2012) opined that visually impaired students who were blind at birth have quite a difference perspective of the world than those students who lost their vision later in life. The first group has a background of learning through hearing, touch, and the other non-visual senses. Because these senses are used more, they become more highly developed especially of them that have received training. However, the second groups have a background of visual experiences on which to draw.

Conclusion

From the result of the findings, it showed that blindness awareness programme (BAP) has change the attitude of sighted students towards students with visual impairment in university of Jos. Based on the result obtained from the data analyzed in the researcher concluded that, to a great extent blindness awareness programme (BAP) has changed the attitude of sighted students towards students with visual impairment in university of Jos, Plateau State To this end, (BAP) can change the attitude

of the ignorant students about students with visual impairment in the posttest treatment/intervention

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. There is need to emphasize more on blindness awareness program (BAP) to change the attitude of sighted students towards students with visual impairment.
2. There is need to emphasize on blindness awareness program (BAP) in the media and other means to change the attitude of the society towards students with visual impairment.
3. There is need for to emphasize on blindness awareness program (BAP) on social media to change the attitude of the society towards students with visual impairment.

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